

Implementation of waste management policy in Kwandang sub-district, north Gorontalo regency,

Bais Kakilo *, Irawaty Igirisa and Rusli Isa

Gorontalo State University Postgraduate Program, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 20(01), 451–457

Publication history: Received on 01 August 2023; revised on 13 September 2023; accepted on 15 September 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.1.1837>

Abstract

This study aims to examine the implementation of the Waste Management Policy in North Gorontalo Regency and the determinants in the implementation of the policy. Research data was collected through interviews, observation, and documentation methods. The results showed that: (1) the implementation of waste management policies in Kwandang Sub-district, North Gorontalo Regency is still not in accordance with the existing PERDA and PERBUP, as seen from the planning that is still not optimal at the sub-district and village government levels, the implementation is still not providing the expected output, and aspects of supervision and evaluation are still very weak and indecisive which causes many repeat violators errors littering; (2) factors that influence waste management policies, namely communication, supporting resources, both human and material resources, as well as bureaucratic attitudes and systems.

Keywords: Policy Implementation; Waste Management; Household Waste

1. Introduction

The waste problem is a challenge that will determine environmental improvement. Waste is one of the important things that must be faced seriously by the government. No wonder the government does not stop educating the public through advertisements displayed on billboards and television media. In dealing with the waste problem, public awareness is needed. By having awareness, people will not litter.

In 2021, according to data from the National Waste Management Information System (SIPSN), waste handling in Indonesia is only at 15,199,027.30 (tons/year) or around 49.37% of the 30,783,820 tons of waste produced by the Indonesian people per year. Based on these data, the level of landfill per year is very high. Not to mention the increasing growth rate of society which will certainly increase the supply of waste. If left unchecked, there will be a buildup of waste that results in disasters, environmental damage, and health problems in the community. In this matter, the government continues to intensify waste management with economic value. Waste is no longer seen as something dirty and must be destroyed, but there is economic value in it if we want to manage waste well. The Indonesia Clean Waste 2025 program proclaims a 30% reduction in waste from the source and recycling of at least 70% of waste so that it does not end up in landfill.

The central government gives full authority to each region to regulate and manage waste under the conditions and policies of each region so that each region is independent of waste treatment in each region. This is supported by Government Regulation Number 81 of 2012 concerning the Management of Household Waste and Similar Household Waste and strengthened by Government Regulation 27 of 2020 concerning Specific Waste Management, namely waste due to the nature of its concentration or volume requiring special management, such as B3 waste. One form of effort to implement the mandate of the Law, the North Gorontalo Regency Government has issued Regent Regulation Number

* Corresponding author: Bais Kakilo

19 of 2018 concerning Management of Household Waste and Similar Waste of Household Waste and Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 concerning Waste Management in North Gorontalo Regency.

The problem of waste management in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency is entering the emergency phase. This is based on an increase in the volume of waste per day. Kwandang District is the economic and government center of Gorontalo Regency, so it is undeniable that community activities in Kwandang District are very high and result in increased waste production. Based on (SIPSN), every day North Gorontalo produces approximately 47 tons of waste, while the facilities and infrastructure supporting waste management are inadequate. Landfills in North Gorontalo should use good and correct waste management technology, such as waste shredders, plastic waste smelting machines, and so on.

Public knowledge about waste handling is still very lacking. In addition, people still lack the awareness to dispose of garbage in its place. This can be seen from the existence of illegal garbage dumps that are increasingly mushrooming, garbage is simply thrown into sewers, rivers, and quiet roadsides, not to mention waste officers whose resources have not been *updated* regarding good and correct waste management.

The purpose of this study is to examine the implementation of the Waste Management Policy in North Gorontalo Regency, in terms of planning, implementation, as well as supervision, and evaluation. In addition, this study also aims to examine the determinants in the implementation of the policy, seen from aspects of communication, resources, attitudes, and bureaucratic systems.

2. Method

This research is descriptive qualitative research. Research data were collected through interviews, observation, and documentation methods. The informants involved in the interview are determined by *purposive techniques*, meaning that the determination of informants according to the depth of information needed. The research data was then analyzed qualitatively.

3. Research Results

3.1. Implementation of Waste Management Policy in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency

3.1.1. Planning

To create a clean and healthy life, an environment that is free from pollution and waste is needed. If the environment is clean and healthy, then community life is also good. If we are right in handling waste, both industrial waste and home waste, it is certain that no environment will be polluted due to the smell of littered and untreated.

Waste management in Kwandang District, Gorontalo Regency refers to Regent Regulation Number 19 of 2018 and Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 with the hope that the planning is well-done and can be carried out by every community. However, in contrast to expectations, the planning and implementation of the policy have not been optimal enough and does not work as it should.

Based on the results of interviews with several informants, it was found that the local government's policy in waste management has not been optimal because the planning is not yet clear. The results of the interview showed, in general, the level of involvement in waste management planning in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency is still very far from expectations because the planning stage which is the foundation and main point of a program has not been carried out properly and correctly. In addition, the level of community involvement in waste management planning has not been thoroughly involved.

3.1.2. Implementation

The Kwandang District Government of North Gorontalo Regency is the executor of the government in the sub-district which houses several villages. The sub-district government should be able to translate the Regent Regulations and Regional Regulations that have been issued by the Regional Government. With the birth of Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 and Regent Regulation Number 19 of 2018, the District Government must socialize and implement these regulations.

Information obtained from several informants shows that the Kwandang District Government has helped the implementation of waste management but has not been optimal. The Kwandang sub-district government only conducts repeated socialization and mobilizes the community to work to clean their respective environments. Meanwhile, technically, waste management from upstream to downstream is carried out by the Environmental Office of North Gorontalo Regency.

According to some parties, in some areas, there are already facilities and infrastructure that support the implementation of waste management. It's just that the existence of these facilities is not supported by qualified human resources. Waste officers should be equipped with waste management knowledge so that the available facilities can be used as well as possible. On the other hand, in some areas, facilities and waste workers are still inadequate. So, people prefer to burn home waste to make it more practical, which, will result in environmental damage.

3.2. Supervision and evaluation

Supervision and evaluation is a very important process. With supervision, policies can be controlled properly. The policy supervision process is carried out by the North Gorontalo Regency Government, in this case, the Civil Service Police Unit Service. Meanwhile, the evaluation was carried out by the Environmental Office of North Gorontalo Regency.

The results of interviews with informants show that supervision and evaluation of waste management policies have been implemented, but they are still not optimal and comprehensive. Enforcement against violators of PERDA and PERBUP is still very weak, and which, only reprimanded and invited to work is to clean up places that are used as illegal garbage dumps. On the other hand, the government also cannot provide stricter sanctions because the government also realizes that waste management facilities in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency are still very limited. Thus, it can be concluded that the waste management policy in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency has not worked as it should. In this case, researchers found that supervision and evaluation were not in accordance with the mandate of Regent Regulation Number 19 of 2018 and Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019.

3.3. Factors Affecting the Implementation of Waste Management Policy in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency

3.3.1. Policymaker communication

Communication is key to policy success. Communication must be carried out properly and correctly so that commands from top to bottom can be connected properly. Good communication can give birth to maximum program and policy success. If communication is not well established, then this communication factor can be an obstacle to the implementation of policies.

Interviews with informants from the Kwandang sub-district government showed that communication had been done very well. The delivery of orders from superiors, from the planning stage, and socialization, to strict sanctions for violators, has been conveyed to the village government and the community. This shows that communication from top to bottom is optimal. However, on the other hand, interviews with village governments show that communication from the bottom up is still not going well. The village government complained that some policies were inappropriate and poorly communicated.

3.3.2. Support resources

Supporting resources, such as infrastructure resources and waste officers in carrying out waste management policies must be adequate. If the supporting resources are problematic, certainly, the implementation of the policy will also be problematic.

Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that the resources supporting waste management policies in Kwandang District are still very minimal, especially in terms of facilities and infrastructure. The public awareness factor is indeed one of the reasons for the failure of the implementation of the management policy. However, it is undeniable that the factor of limited facilities and infrastructure is also one of the reasons the garbage is scattered and not taken care of.

3.3.3. Government bureaucratic attitudes and systems

The attitude and bureaucratic system of government in a government can determine the course of government. If the leader's attitude is not firm in carrying out policies, then it can be a loophole for the community to make violations. Not

to mention if the bureaucratic system is too rigid and monotonous. The policies contained in the programs will be increasingly difficult to implement.

Based on the results of the interview, it can be concluded that bureaucratic attitudes and systems must be highlighted in deciding. The policy will be implemented if the government's attitude as a policymaker is firm and serious. The bureaucratic system that is run must be completely transparent and relevant to the policies implemented. A healthy bureaucratic system can be seen from the good relationships created in government.

Related to the government's attitude towards waste management issues in Kwandang District. According to researchers, the government is less firm in addressing this waste problem. This can be seen from the absence of clear sanctions for waste violators who deliberately throw garbage anywhere. It is evident that mountains of visible garbage are everywhere and unkempt, not to mention the monotonous government bureaucratic system from top to bottom.

4. Discussion

4.1. Implementation of Waste Management Policy in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency

4.1.1. Planning

Garbage is a dirty waste and must be destroyed. However, its destruction must be done properly. Otherwise, such garbage may cause other problems. The waste consists of two types, namely organic and inorganic waste. Organic waste comes from nature such as tree leaves, food scraps, and animal carcasses. Organic waste itself can be easily decomposed back by the soil. Inorganic waste is the remains of chemicals containing materials, such as mineral bottles, batteries, glass, and plastic. This inorganic waste is very difficult to be decomposed by the soil, it even takes hundreds of years to be able to decompose the inorganic waste.

The problem of waste is no longer a trivial issue. In handling waste, careful and directed planning is needed. Human growth is currently unstoppable so human needs and waste production are also increasing. If this waste problem is not taken seriously from now on, what will happen is that environmental pollution will get worse which will have an impact on public health.

In waste management in Kwandang District, the planning stage has been carried out by the North Gorontalo Regency government, in this case, the Environmental Agency. The purpose of this plan is intended to maximize and improve waste management in Kwandang District. But on the contrary, it was found that waste management in Kwandang District was still not optimal and had not run as it should. Talking about waste management planning in Kwandang District should be implemented properly and correctly. But in reality, the socialization carried out by the sub-district government has not been optimal. Waste management policy planning is only at the official level, while for sub-district and village governments, it has not been maximized.

In general, waste management planning in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency is still very far from expectations because the planning stage which is the foundation and principal of a program has not been carried out properly and correctly. In addition, the level of community involvement in waste management planning has not been thoroughly involved. Involving the community in planning has its benefits for the success of the program. For example, by collecting mandatory levies for the community. By collecting retribution for the community, the community gets services in the form of officers who pick up the garbage and dispose of garbage. The waste levy in North Gorontalo has long been regulated in the PERDA, which is contained in Regional Regulation Number 17 of 2014 concerning Waste/Hygiene Service Retribution but is not implemented.

4.1.2. Implementation

The North Gorontalo Regency Government through the Environmental Office investigated the waste problem in Kwandang District and other sub-districts by issuing Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 and Regent Regulation Number 19 of 2018. Based on the results of the interview, information was obtained that the Regional Government's policy regarding waste management in Kwandang District has not been optimal because it has not had a positive impact on environmental cleanliness in general. The results of the interview show in general that waste management in Kwandang District is still far from expectations because the scattered waste is still very much and disturbs the community. This is shown by data in 2022, the waste production in North Gorontalo Regency is 47 tons per day, while the waste that can be handled is only approximately 28 tons per day. That is, what cannot be managed is 19 tons per day. This unmanageable garbage has quite basic reasons. In districts with very high waste production, there is no

adequate waste transport fleet, facilities and infrastructure in the form of landfills are limited, public awareness is very minimal, and sanctions for violators are not applied optimally. These reasons make the amount of garbage in Kwandang District scattered everywhere and not maintained.

The waste management policy has not been optimal because it has not yet had the effect of reducing the use of 30% of waste from household waste and similar household waste in 2025 according to the objectives of PERBUP. From the results of the interview, it can be concluded that the landfill in North Gorontalo from 2019 to 2022 has not decreased but has increased. Judging from the waste handling process, the government has indeed worked well, but the problems that have occurred so far, the implementation process still refers to the limits of the ability of waste officers who try to maximize minimal facilities and infrastructure. Plus, the knowledge of waste officers is also not given more knowledge for the development of knowledge about waste management properly and correctly. From the observations of researchers, waste officers who are recorded as honorees whose salary is equated with other honorees who work in the room are the main factors that are not optimal work of the waste officer. The salary of waste officers who work from 05.00 WIB to 16.00 WIB is the same as the salary of honorees who work in offices from 07.30 to 15.00 WIB. Not to mention such a large workload, such as sweeping, collecting, sorting, and transporting garbage from temporary landfills to final landfills.

4.1.3. Supervision and evaluation

In maximizing a policy, it is very important to supervise the implementation process. By conducting supervision, the perpetrators of waste violators can be immediately reprimanded. Likewise, in the process of socialization and implementation of policies to the sub-district government and village government, supervision can be known for which sub-districts and villages have not gone through the planning stage as the first step in the process of implementing policies by the community.

In the process of supervision, the sanctions and actions that will be given to violators were regulated. Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019 in Chapter XIX states that administrative sanctions for violators are determined as follows:

- Rebuke
- Written warning
- Government coercion
- Forced money
- License revocation
- Business closure of activities

However, its application is not in accordance with what has been formulated in the PERDA.

The supervision of waste management policies in Kwandang District is expected to reduce violations of throwing waste anywhere. Nevertheless, this expectation does not correspond to reality. The large amount of waste that is not managed is evidence of the ineffectiveness of sanctions and supervisory functions in this policy.

4.2. Factors Affecting the Implementation of Waste Management Policy in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency

4.2.1. Policymaker communication

In a policy, communication is one of the keys to successful policy implementation. From the planning stage, communication must run well and correctly. Communication can connect the aims and objectives of a program. Communication can be done from top to bottom and from bottom to top. If communication is done correctly, the aims and objectives will be well programmed and will give birth to a policy.

From the interviews, researchers concluded that the waste management policy in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency has not run optimally due to interrupted communication. Waste management policy planning only exists at the level of the Environment Agency, while the District Government and Village Government waste management policy planning has not been implemented. It has been involved at the planning stage but only in the form of socialization.

4.2.2. Support resources

The most important factor influencing waste management policy is supporting resources. In organizations, be it private organizations or government organizations, some resources are expected to achieve goals efficiently and with good management. These resources are human resources and material resources, both of which are very important management elements, especially human elements because this element holds importance in moving other elements to achieve the goals of the organization. The achievement of efficiency and effectiveness can be successful when each user of time, energy, and other resources can make an optimal contribution to an organizational goal that is largely determined by the ability of its workforce or employees. Changes and organizational development are related to the terms put forward. The goal is sometimes written officially but sometimes it is also only seen in action.

Judging from supporting resources, based on the results of the study, it is known that supporting resources are one of the factors that can affect waste management in Kwandang District, Gorontalo Regency. This is because human resources and material resources can be indicators of successful waste management. Waste workers who do not have knowledge and expertise in managing waste will result in poor performance in waste management. Facilities and infrastructure will also affect poor waste management in Kwandang District. From data taken from the Environmental Agency, the garbage hauling fleet only has 3 units of trucks, 8 temporary landfills, and one final landfill. When viewed from the area of North Gorontalo Regency and the population, the facilities and infrastructure are very minimal.

4.2.3. Government bureaucratic attitudes and systems

In addition to resources, other factors are attitudes and bureaucratic systems. Attitudes and bureaucratic systems are one of the influencing factors that can affect waste management policies. This is because, in implementing policies that have been formulated, the attitude of policy formulators is very necessary to affirm the application following applicable regulations. The government's bureaucratic system also influences the affirmation of the application of these regional regulations. If the bureaucratic system has a firm and disciplined attitude in running, it can be ascertained that the implementation of waste management policies can run as expected. But the government's attitude as a controller and supervisor of policy towards violators is not so firm. Many violations are deliberately committed by both individuals and companies. This attitude can make weaknesses in the affirmation of local regulations.

From the results of the study, researchers concluded that the attitude and system of government bureaucracy towards waste management in Kwandang District, North Gorontalo Regency needs to be maximized. The government's attitude in terms of affirmation of violators of PERDA must be firmer. This lack of assertiveness is what becomes an opening for violators to continue to make mistakes and continue to repeat mistakes. Sanctions for violators of littering have been regulated in Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019, but the weak attitude and bureaucratic system make the PERDA like a display that is not carried out.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research that has been described, it can be concluded that:

The implementation of the waste management policy in the Kwandang sub-district, North Gorontalo Regency has not been in accordance with Regent Regulation Number 19 of 2018 and Regional Regulation Number 6 of 2019. This can be seen from: (a) Planning that must involve all elements of society as objects of policy objectives has not been maximally involved. Planning is still at the official level, while waste management planning at the sub-district and village government levels has not been maximized, (b) aspects of policy implementation still do not provide *output*. This is because the policy still finds many deviations from what has previously been formulated, (c) the supervision/evaluation aspect is still very weak, resulting in many violators who repeat waste disposal errors due to weak supervision and evaluation of the policy.

Factors that affect waste management policies are: (a) implementor communication, which needs to be considered is command communication from top to bottom and from bottom to top. This means that communication in the form of orders from superiors to subordinates and communication in the form of suggestions and input from subordinates to superiors must run well and harmoniously to achieve policy objectives effectively and efficiently, (b) supporting resources. Quality human resources understand and master good waste management as well as material resources such as good finance and facilities are the main factors for the success of waste management policies, (c) bureaucratic attitudes and systems. Bureaucratic attitudes and systems are one of the factors that can affect the implementation of waste management policies. This is because the implementation of regional regulations requires a firm attitude and consistent attitude from the government. A good democratic system gives birth to effective and efficient policy implementation.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Aini, A. F. (2014). Analysis of Waste Management Implementation on UNSRI Campus. *Journal of Public Administration*.
- [2] Central Bureau of Statistics North Gorontalo Regency. Population growth by sub-district. <https://gorontaloutarakab.bps.go.id/> retrieved 25 November 2022
- [3] Hargo.co.id North Gorontalo produces 47 tons of waste every day. <https://hargo.co.id/berita/setiap-hari-gorontalo-utara-produksi-sampah-sebanyak-47-ton/> Retrieved 20 November 2022
- [4] Harsono, p. (2002). *Policy and Political Implementation*. Jakarta: Grafindo Jaya.
- [5] Isa, r. (2011). *Effectiveness of the Collection of the Levy and Cleanliness in Increasing the Original Income of the Original Income of the*. Gorontalo: International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology.
- [6] Kadir, A. (2020). *Public Policy Governance in the Perspective of Public Administration in Indonesia*. Medan: CV Darma Persada.
- [7] Notoatmodjo. (2007). *Analysis of Household Waste Management*. Bandung : Learning Library.
- [8] Pasolong, H. (2019). *Theory of Public Administration* . Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [9] Regent Regulation Number 19 of 2018. Retrieved December 5, 2022. On the <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/132360/perbup-kab-gorontalo-utara-no-19-tahun-2018> page
- [10] Regional Regulation of North Gorontalo Regency Number 6 of 2019. Retrieved December 5, 2022. On the [https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/ page of perda-kab-gorontalo-utara-no-6 tahun-2019](https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/page_of_perda-kab-gorontalo-utara-no-6_tahun-2019)
- [11] Riant, N. (2003). *Public Policy, Formulation, Implementation and Evaluation*. Jakarta: Elex Media Komputindo.
- [12] Santoso. (2008). *Public Policy Process and Analysis*. Jakarta: Intermedia.
- [13] Subarsono, A. (2010). *Public Policy Analysis, Concepts, Theory and Affliction*. Yogyakarta: Learning Library.
- [14] Tahir, A. (2020). *Public Administration, Good Governance Towards Sound Government*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- [15] Tri, Y. (2020). Waste Management in Sepatang Area, Tangerang Regency. *Journal of Public Administration*.
- [16] Wahab, a. (2004). *Policy Analysis and Formulation to State Policy Implementation*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [17] Winardi, B. (2003). *Human Resource Management*. Yogyakarta.
- [18] Winarno, B. (2012). *Public Policy, Theory, Process and Case Studies*. Jakarta: Chalia Indonesia.
- [19] Jonah. (2014). *Policy Planning, Implementation and Evaluation (Management Function)*. Majalengka: Publishing Unit of Majalengka University.
- [20] Zainal, D. K. (2020). Waste Management in Sepatang Area, Tangerang Regency. *Journal of Public Administration of Gaja Mada university*.